

Analysis of the Perception of Teaching Methods at Laval University by Senegalese Students

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to analyze the perception of pedagogical methods by Senegalese students of Laval University. To achieve this objective, a research problem was developed around teaching methods. The theoretical framework is based on teacher-centeredness and actualizing pedagogical methods. The methodology employed a qualitative approach, using a case study as the research tradition. The participants consist of students enrolled at the University who began their university studies in Senegal. Three students were selected using purposive sampling. To gather data, a semi-structured interview guide was created. Finally, regarding the results, they indicate that Senegalese students have a certain perception of the pedagogical methods used by teachers at Laval University. These students also encounter difficulties in adapting to these methods.

Keywords: students, pedagogical methods, teacher-centeredness, actualizing pedagogy, case study.

Résumé

Cette étude a pour objectif d'analyser la perception des méthodes pédagogiques par les enseignants de l'Université Laval de l'Université Laval par les étudiants sénégalais. Pour atteindre cet objectif, une problématique a été développée autour des méthodes d'enseignement. Quant au cadre théorique, il repose sur le magistro-centrisme et les méthodes pédagogiques actualisantes. Pour la méthodologie, c'est l'approche qualitative qui été utilisées avec l'étude de cas comme tradition de recherche. Les sujets sont constitués des étudiants inscrits à l'Université, mais ayant entamé les études universitaires au Sénégal. Au nombre de trois, les étudiants ont été sélectionné par la méthode d'échantillonnage à choix raisonné. Pour recueillir les données, un guide d'entretien demi-dirigé a été confectionné. Enfin concernant les résultats, ils montrent que les étudiants sénégalais ont une certaine perception des méthodes pédagogiques utilisées par les enseignants de l'Université Laval. Ces derniers rencontrent également des difficultés pour s'adapter à ces méthodes.

Mots-clés : étudiants, méthodes pédagogiques, magistro-centrisme, pédagogie actualisantes, étude de cas.

Introduction

In Francophone Africa, the traditional teaching model strongly influences pedagogical practices. Consequently, the emphasis often lies in knowledge transmission rather than empowering learners. The designed curricula aim for general objectives without considering learning outcomes (Kahn & Rey, 2008). According to Vienneau (2006), a learning outcome is neither an objective nor a strategy. It approaches teaching from a different perspective : while objectives specify what the teacher should do, outcomes describe what the student should have learned by the end of a year (Vienneau, 2006). In this type of teaching, the student is seen as a mere subject to act upon. As stated by Not (1979, p.7), "one wants to teach, instruct, train. One teaches a subject to children, meaning one faces two objects: the subject matter and the child; the student is taken out of their child state, directed, shaped, and equipped." These are the teacher-centered or traditional pedagogical methods. In other words, it's a "transmissive mode with normative orientation (MTP1), describing knowledge as objective and cumulative, a pedagogy of the model (and deviation from the model) justifying a positive detour to access it" (Astolfi, 2006, p. 8).

Traditional pedagogical methods correspond to those often prevalent in schools and universities in Senegal. Indeed, most Senegalese educational institutions employ a teaching approach based primarily on the teacher transmitting knowledge to the learner (Gauthier, 2005). With these methods, the learner becomes passive and relies on the teacher for everything. In this type of learning, the teacher prepares the material they will dictate to the students after some explanation of the content (Ndoye, 2000). According to Ndoye (2000), this is often due not only to the attachment to traditional teaching methods but also

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to the often overcrowded class sizes. In Senegal, it's not uncommon to have classes with over 2000 students in the first and/or second year of university.

On the other hand, in North American universities like Laval University, pedagogical methods prioritize the learner. In these universities, the knowledge transmission process relies on learner independence. Here, teachings are more individual-oriented, taking into account the student's background and experiences. The objective is to assist the learner in constructing their own knowledge with the support of the teacher (Gauthier, 2005). Furthermore, several studies, including Viens, Lepage & Karsenti's (2010), mention a correlation between socio-cultural background and students' difficulties in adapting to certain aspects.

Presenting the context of pedagogical methods allows us to perceive a difference in the teaching approaches used in Senegalese universities and at Laval University. This difference is experienced by Senegalese students currently attending Laval University. This has motivated us to conduct this study, whose objective is to analyze the perception of teaching methods at Laval University by Senegalese students.

Theoretical Framework and Methodology

Theoretical Framework

To study the perception of teaching methods at Laval University by Senegalese students, a theoretical framework is constructed around traditional (Houssaye, 2014 and Gauthier, 1997) and modern (Luckerhoff, Johnson & Guillemette, 2020 and Landry, 2002) pedagogical methods. It is observed that the majority of Senegalese schools and universities practice a teaching approach primarily based on magistro-centrism. This pedagogical tradition is characterized by "seven traits: centrality of the teacher, impersonality of the relationship, strict asymmetry, transmission of knowledge detached from life, highly normative educational ideal, bureaucratic arrangement, charismatic model" (Houssaye, 2014, p. 212). This teaching method primarily relies on lectures, where the teacher is the sole authority in the classroom (Gauthier, 1997).

However, traditional pedagogical methods need to evolve as learners have become increasingly demanding. We are now in an era of innovative pedagogical methods. Indeed, "students are required to discover realities through systematic observation of facts and experiences, and then use conceptual and theoretical tools to construct an understanding of those realities. This approach breaks away from traditional teaching, which discloses theories, and engages students more in constructing their learning" (Luckerhoff, Johnson & Guillemette, 2020).

With the new teaching methods, the learner becomes the architect of their own knowledge. As for the teacher, they act as a facilitator who coordinates the pedagogical activities in the classroom. This marks the rise of actualizing pedagogy, which "encourages problem-solving in groups and the development of social skills conducive to teamwork" (Landry, 2002, p. 20).

In Senegal, the reliance on traditional pedagogical methods can be attributed mainly to two essential reasons. Firstly, introducing change into any system is not an easy task. Resistance to change is common, with many individuals continuing to adhere to traditional teaching methods, as mentioned earlier, where the teacher is the sole authority of knowledge. The other reason for difficulties in changing pedagogical methods in Senegal relates to class sizes. From kindergarten to secondary school, class sizes are often very large (it's not uncommon to have 80 students in a single classroom). In this context, the most suitable pedagogical model for teaching children is the traditional one. However, things are gradually changing, especially in vocational training schools where innovative methods are increasingly being used. Additionally, since the advent of COVID-19, some teaching is conducted remotely.

Methodology

As per Johnson & Christensen (2008), research methodology should not only allow readers to judge the researcher's approach but also enable its replication if needed. It must be precise and comprehensive. In this regard, our methodological approach will revolve around the following aspects: research type, research subject identification, sampling, data collection, data processing, and analysis. Considering the limited number of participants, this research employs a qualitative approach. According to Mays & Pope (1995, p. 43), "the goal of qualitative research is to develop concepts that help us understand social phenomena in natural (rather than experimental) settings, focusing on the meanings, experiences, and viewpoints of all participants." Furthermore, qualitative research comprises five traditions : Biography, Phenomenology, Grounded Theory, Ethnography, and Case Study (Creswell, 1999).

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Unlike quantitative approaches, qualitative methods often study small groups. Therefore, within the scope of this research, we have chosen a case study. This is particularly justified by the small number of participants in the study. According to Creswell & Miller (2000), a case study involves collecting multiple sources of information, including observations, interviews, audiovisual material, and various documents. After analyzing this information, the next step involves a thorough description of the studied cases (Creswell & Miller, 2000).

In other words, a case study allows for exploring a specific question through one or more precise, delimited, and contextualized cases (Creswell, 2003). In this study, the cases consist of three Senegalese students enrolled at Laval University. The number of cases is sufficient; in fact, according to Stake (2010), an sample size is never small in qualitative research. Thus, the study could even focus on a single individual or case (Stake, 2010). For the selection of these three research subjects, the non-probabilistic purposive sampling method was employed. According to Royer and Zarlowsk (2014), sampling refers to methods of selecting a subset of individuals from a population to estimate its characteristics. Regarding data collection, it was conducted individually with the research subjects. In other words, we conducted interviews with each student using a semi-structured interview guide specifically designed for this purpose. The guide predominantly consisted of open-ended questions to avoid mutual influences on participants' responses. According to Savoie-Zajc (2009, p. 340), "a semi-structured interview involves a flexible interaction between the researcher and the participant. The researcher allows the rhythm and unique content of the exchange to guide them, aiming to approach the general themes they wish to explore with the research participant. Through this interaction, a rich understanding of the phenomenon under study is jointly constructed with the interviewer." Each interview lasted between five (5) to ten (10) minutes. Finally, to maintain the anonymity of respondents, we assigned them codes. Thus, ERQ1 represents the first student, ERQ2 the second, and ERQ3 the last student. The interviews were recorded with the students' consent. After the interviews, the participants' statements were transcribed, coded, and categorized before undergoing analysis.

Analysis and Discussion of Results

In this section, the analysis and discussion will revolve around the verbatim content derived from the interviews conducted with the three students. The work will be organized around three themes as outlined in the interview guide. These themes include the description of teaching methods used in Senegal, those employed at Laval University, and the subjects' comparison of these two teaching methods.

Teaching Methods Used in Senegal

Regarding the pedagogical methods used in Senegal, it must be highlighted from the outset that the interviewed students characterized them as directive or transmission-based methods. As mentioned in the introduction, the teaching methods frequently employed in Senegal are primarily centered around the transmission of knowledge from the teacher to the student. In this type of teaching, the student is passive and relies heavily on the teacher (Gauthier, 2005).

This characterization is confirmed by the Senegalese students with whom we conducted interviews. To illustrate this, here is what ERQ2 stated: "Teaching methods in Senegal are essentially transmission-based, with a near absence of group work." However, while ERQ2 is clear about the transmission-based nature of the pedagogical approaches used in Senegalese universities, this is not the case for the other students, namely ERQ1 and ERQ3. ERQ1 indicated that there are two pedagogical approaches used in Senegal: the participatory approach and the directive approach. They stated, "I would say that in Senegal, in terms of teaching methods, two main tendencies emerge."

In discussing directive methods, ERQ1 confirmed the stance of ERQ2 regarding the existence of directive pedagogical methods where students are passive. In these methods, the teacher is the main holder of knowledge and imparts it to the students. This implies that with such teaching methods, students contribute little effort as they receive almost everything from their teacher. To support this analysis, ERQ1 mentioned, "The first (pedagogical approach) is a directive tendency where the teacher imparts most of the teachings and guides the students, and students tend to engage with this approach. It's thus a directive approach." Additionally, alongside this directive or transmission-based approach, there exists a more flexible participatory approach. Here, the learner is fully engaged in constructing knowledge. In this context, it's the students themselves who build their own knowledge, in contrast to the directive approach. ERQ1 stated, "There have also been more flexible approaches, let's say active approaches that encourage student participation." ERQ3 concurred with their compatriot ERQ1, emphasizing that the pedagogical methods used in Senegal are at times active or participatory. ERQ3 even went further to suggest that these methods are almost the same as those practiced at Laval University. ERQ3 stated, "(...) but it's mostly the teaching methods we

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use, meaning methods that are primarily centered on active student participation in the process of knowledge acquisition." However, it's noticeable that ERQ3 exercises caution when saying "mostly the teaching methods," which implies that there might be differences.

The varying perceptions that Senegalese students hold about the pedagogical methods used in Senegal can be explained by the fact that both ERQ1 and ERQ3 attended vocational training schools where students are selected through a highly competitive process. In these schools, teachers can afford to use active or participatory teaching methods as their student numbers are limited. ERQ2, on the other hand, attended Cheikh Anta Diop University in Dakar, where class sizes can be extremely large, sometimes exceeding 2000 students. With such numbers, it becomes challenging for teachers to implement active or participatory teaching methods. In fact, ERQ3 even mentioned, "(...) since we don't have many universities, class sizes are massive, and there aren't many professors, so we end up with professors teaching in lecture halls with over 2500 students (...)." This situation reaffirms the notion that the number of students determines the teaching methods employed.

Teaching Methods Used at Laval University

According to the three students we interviewed, the teaching methods used by instructors at Laval University are rooted in active pedagogy. These are methods that grant more autonomy to learners. With these methods, the teacher becomes a facilitator who guides students through the process of knowledge acquisition. In other words, the teacher's presence in the classroom involves guiding and directing students who are the builders of their own knowledge. This observation was unanimous among the interviewees. To illustrate this, ERQ1 stated, "(...) but if I try to characterize the teaching methods at Laval University a bit, I do notice that there is a significant part where there is guidance that allows the student to develop their autonomy." This indicates that student autonomy is highly developed in the pedagogical approaches practiced at Laval University. According to our respondents, this can be largely attributed to the availability of resources. Unlike the universities they came from, Laval University provides students with abundant documentary resources. These include electronic documents as well as physical resources like course materials, textbooks, periodicals, etc. Referring to this abundance of resources, ERQ3 mentioned, "(...) I can say that here students have more resources, more textbooks, more reference materials; in short, they have more opportunities to access information."

However, in their perceptions of the pedagogical approaches used at Laval University, some students also raised criticisms. This is noteworthy as it is known that not everything is always perfect in the pedagogical approaches at any institution. Thus, for these students, the teaching methods depend on the instructors. Indeed, in their view, some professors at Laval University are often inactive, leading to frequent student presentations. In essence, students end up doing most of the work instead of the professor. This shows that students are not indifferent to what professors do. They mention the lack of effort put forth by some instructors during classes. The words of ERQ3 below exemplify this sentiment : "(...) I don't appreciate it at all because sometimes I think it's a bit too easy..., the professors don't put in enough effort, it's the students who do everything."

Comparison between Pedagogical Methods

Regarding the differentiation between the pedagogical approaches used at Laval University and those practiced in Senegal, the participants in this study emphasized student autonomy and personal development. In Senegal, students often remain reliant on the knowledge transmitted by instructors, while in North America in general, and specifically at Laval University, the teaching aims to foster personal development among students. This is reflected in the role of the instructors as facilitators during classes. ERQ1 mentioned, "However, here at Laval University, from the start, you are provided with tools, guidelines, and directions that give you the opportunity to enhance your intellectual capacities, your potential. To gather information, to develop the habits of work and intellectual production." This indicates that at Laval University, instructors encourage students to take pleasure in constructing their own knowledge.

The comparison of the two pedagogical approaches reveals a significant difference between Laval University and Senegalese universities, particularly in terms of the organization of the academic year and program configuration. ERQ2 stated, "No, it's not the same at all; it's even linked to the program structure (...)." In Canada, the academic year is organized into sessions and courses are divided into credits, unlike in Senegal where teaching takes place throughout the year (9 to 10 months). To emphasize this difference, ERQ2 mentioned, "Here (at Laval University), it's by session, and each session lasts for 4 months, unlike back home where it's 9 months."

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Moreover, Senegal has also implemented the LMD (Bachelor-Master-Doctorate) reform. With this reform, the academic year is organized into semesters, and courses are organized into teaching units with credits. ERQ2 illustrated this point, "With the LMD reform, we are moving towards the concept of credits, semesterization, and dividing the year into multiple sessions."

Furthermore, this study revealed that there are no significant differences between the pedagogical approaches of Laval University and those used in Senegal, especially in higher vocational training schools. This is primarily due to the relatively small number of students attending these institutions. ERQ3, who is a teacher at one of these schools, mentioned, "In fact, between the pedagogical methods used at Laval University and those used in the department where I work, there aren't major differences." However, he acknowledged that there is a difference in approach between Senegalese universities and Laval University. He attributed this difference to the overcrowded student populations found in Senegalese universities, saying, "But if you compare the pedagogical methods used at Laval University and those used in Senegalese universities, there are indeed significant differences."

Conclusion

The objective of this study was to analyze the perception of teaching methods at Laval University by Senegalese students. To achieve this goal, a research problem was developed around traditional and innovative pedagogical methods. In terms of methodology, the study employed a qualitative approach with the research tradition of a case study. The selection of students for interviews was done using purposive sampling.

The results reveal that the students interviewed hold a positive view of the teaching methods used at Laval University. For some, these methods are considered active, fostering student empowerment. Moreover, students appreciate the availability of documentary resources that enable them to independently seek out and construct their own knowledge. However, while some students view the teaching methods positively, others offer a more critical perspective. For these individuals, there is a perceived connection between teaching methods and the instructors who employ them. Consequently, certain professors at Laval University are seen as inactive, leading to a reliance on readings and student presentations during classes.

Furthermore, it would be interesting to delve deeper into two points raised by the respondents: program flexibility and the lack of effort by instructors. While the respondents appreciate the flexibility to take courses outside their program, they remain critical of the teaching methods of certain professors. These aspects will be subject to further analysis in a forthcoming article.

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